

Bank Syariah Indonesia (BSI): Mapping Research Topics using Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics

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Abstract

This research aims to map research topics surrounding Bank Syariah Indonesia (BSI) with a qualitative approach, which is in the nature of a library research. The data collection technique is: first, open the Perish/Harzing software, then search for journals based on the title words category with the key word " Bank Syariah Indonesia (BSI) " within the entire year period. Second, collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles. Third, download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) format from all journals for which data has been collected. Fourth, enter the RIS data file into Mendeley software Desktop. Data analysis technique by mapping research topics around Bank Syariah Indonesia (BSI) based on the journals that have been collected. The research results show that There are 8 Mapping Research Topics using literature studies regarding Bank Syariah Indonesia, namely: (1) Financial performance; (2) Employee performance; (3) Customer behavior; (4) Financing/credit products; (5) Savings/deposit products; (6) Mergers; (7) Digitalization & technology; and (8) Other issues. The implication and contribution of this research is the mapping of research topics surrounding Bank Syariah Indonesia (BSI), whether frequently or rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the gaps in research on this topic.

Keywords: Bank Syariah Indonesia (BSI); Library Research; Bibliometrics; VOSviewer

Introduction

Islamic banking in Indonesia has shown rapid progress in the modern economy, especially in Indonesia. Indonesia is a country with a majority Muslim population. This can increase public interest in sharia banking activities. Therefore, sharia banking in Indonesia is the best solution for society. One of the popular sharia banks in Indonesia currently is Bank Syariah Indonesia (BSI).

BSI is an Indonesian bank that operates in the sharia banking sector. This bank was founded through the process of merging Bank Syariah Mandiri and BNI Syariah to become Bank Rakyat Indonesia Syariah. BSI was officially launched and introduced to the public on February 1 2021. Based on the information contained in The State of Global Islamic Economy Report after the Bank merged, Bank Syariah Indonesia was ranked 7th in national banks based on assets. BSI has a very important role in improving the Indonesian economy, especially in the field of sharia banking, because it is hoped that it can provide a new, more diverse financial institution for the community.

Research on BSI is also increasing from year to year. A search for articles/journals via the Garuda website shows that in 2021 there will be 235 studies on BSI. This shows that BSI's development is quite rapid and is considered one of the main topics in the field of sharia banking in Indonesia.

The aim of this research is to map research topics surrounding Bank Syariah Indonesia (BSI) using library research (library research). The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains all research topics regarding Bank Syariah Indonesia (BSI), so that it can be a reference for other researchers. The implication and contribution of this research is the mapping of research topics surrounding Bank Syariah Indonesia (BSI), whether frequently or rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the gaps in research on this topic.

Literature Review

Bank Syariah Indonesia (BSI) is a financial institution in Indonesia that is based on Islamic law, which began with a merger process by BUMN. Like other Sharia banks, BSI also focuses on halal profits which is usually called a profit sharing system. The entire operational system is carried out based on the principles of sharia law issued through fatwa no. 130/DSN-MUI/X/2019.

Library research is a type of research that focuses on the analysis, understanding and synthesis of existing literature in a particular field of knowledge or topic. The aim of literature study research is to identify the latest developments, weaknesses, strengths, findings and trends in the relevant research field. In contrast to experimental research or field research, literature study research does not involve collecting primary data through observation, interviews, or experiments. Instead, researchers collect data from secondary sources such as books, scientific journals, articles and other academic documents. After collecting data, researchers then analyze, compare, and organize the literature to achieve a deeper understanding of the topic under study.

Bibliometric studies are a research method used to analyze and measure scientific publications in a particular field, using quantitative data. In bibliometric studies, the data analyzed includes information about the number of publications, authors, subjects, publication sources, citations, and impact factor. The goal of bibliometric studies is to provide an overview of trends and patterns in scientific publications, as well as measure the impact of these publications on the academic community and industry. Bibliometric studies can be used to identify emerging research areas, measure research performance, and compare performance between researchers, institutions, or countries. Bibliometric studies are usually carried out using bibliometric software, such as Web of Science, Scopus, or Google Scholar. Bibliometric methods can also be used to conduct qualitative analysis, such as content analysis or other qualitative analysis, to understand the issues expressed in certain scientific publications.

VOSviewer is open source software used in bibliometric studies to visualize and analyze the network of links between documents or scientific publications. VOSviewer can be used to analyze bibliometric data collected from various sources, such as Scopus, Web of Science, or Google Scholar. VOSviewer can be used to perform quantitative and qualitative analysis, such as cluster identification, citation analysis, and topic mapping. In cluster analysis, VOSviewer can group scientific publications into similar groups based on their association with a particular topic. Citation analysis can be used to identify the most cited scientific publications in a research field. Topic mapping can be used to identify the most widely discussed research topics in a field. One of the advantages of VOSviewer is its ability to produce attractive and easy-to-understand visualizations, such as heatmaps, network graphs and topic trees.

This visualization can help researchers understand patterns and trends in bibliometric data more easily and quickly. VOSviewer can be used by researchers, academics, and practitioners in various research fields, including social science, information science, health, and information technology.

Methodology

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in Library Research studies. The object of the research is Bank Syariah Indonesia. The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is scientific publication articles about Bank Syariah Indonesia originating from national and accredited journals. The source of data collection comes from the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba). Data analysis tools are Microsoft Excel, Mendeley Desktop, VOSviewer, and Perish software.

Data collection techniques include: (1) visiting the Garuda website and Perish software, then search for journal titles based on the title words category with the keyword " Bank Syariah Indonesia " for the entire year (20 2 1-2022); (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping RIS data files on Mendeley Desktop based on year, author and publisher; (2) mapping the results of bibliometric network visualization and scientific publication trends using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) map topics, methods, research findings, and research gaps based on Library Research studies.

Results and Discussion

Mapping the distribution of Scientific Publications about Indonesian Sharia Banks

The results of searching scientific publications regarding Bank Syariah Indonesia in the period 2021 to 2022 show that there are fluctuations or ups and downs every year, especially in the last two years. In 2022, there will be the most publications of 153 articles and in 2021, there will be publications of 80 articles.

Table 1. Scientific publication data about Indonesian Sharia Banks by year

Year of Publication	Number of Publication Articles
2021	80
2022	153
Amount	233

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 201 6.

In table 2, it is shown that the institution/affiliate that most frequently publishes research articles about Bank Syariah Indonesia is Al-Mashrafiyah

(Journal of Sharia Economics, Finance and Banking) with a total of 11 articles published in a period of two years.

Table 2. Affiliation/institution of journal publishers about Indonesian Sharia Bank

Name of Affiliate/Institution	Number of Publications
Al-Mashrafiyah (Journal of Sharia Economics, Finance and Banking)	11
COMSERVA Indonesian Journal of Community Services and Development, etihad: journal of Islamic banking and finance, el aswaq	6
AdBispreneur: Journal of Thought and Research in Business Administration and Entrepreneurship, ADILLA: Journal of Islamic economics	5
Al Iqtishod: Journal of Islamic Economic Thought and Research, Al Maal: Journal of Islamic economics and banking	4
AL-ARBAH: Journal of Islamic Finance and Banking, Al IQTISHAD, AL Qanun, Al Qardh	3
AL-Qisthu, Al-Sharf, An-Nisbah, Al-Urban, Asian Journal of Islamic Management (AJIM), Assyarikah, ASY SYARIYYAH, AT TAWASUTH, BALANCE: journal of accounting and management, BAREKENG: Journal of Mathematics and Applied Sciences, Bertuah: journal of sharia and Islamic economics, Bima Journal, Bisei, Budapest international research and critics institute, building of informatic technology and science, cash flow, center of knowledge, economic image, coopetation.	2

Source: Data processed, Microsoft Excel 20 16.

In table 3, it can be seen that the most productive researcher regarding Bank Syariah Indonesia (BSI) is Muhammad, with a total of 5 articles published.

Table 3. Productivity of researchers around Bank Syariah Indonesia

Researcher	Number of Publications
Mohammed	5
A nggraini, A nis, D amayanti, K husnul, M. I hsan, R eni R ia A rmayani H asibuan	3
A hmad A min, A l R asyid, A malia, A nisatul, A sriana, A uliah E ka, D alimunte, D evy, G ustiawati, H amsir, H ana, H usriah	2

Source: Data processed, Microsoft Excel 20 16. _

Bibliometric Mapping of Research on Indonesian Sharia Banks

Based on search results on the Garuda website, 233 research articles were found discussing Bank Syariah Indonesia. Then, the 233 articles were exported in RIS format and input and analyzed using VOSviewer. The results are as follows:

Figure 1. Network visualization of research development maps regarding Indonesian Sharia Banks

Source: Processed data, software VOSViewer 1.6.18.

co-word map network visualization of research developments regarding Indonesian Sharia Banks are grouped into 7 clusters of 127 topics, as follows:

- Cluster 1. The color red consists of 46 topics, namely: analysis, coefficient, customer decision, customer interest, customer loyalty, customer satisfaction, decision, determination, dimension, effect, employee, employee performance, goal, hypothesis, hypothesis testing, increase, influence, insignificant effect, job satisfaction, knowledge, loyalty, marketing mix, mobile banking, mobile banking service, motivation, multiple linear regression, multiple linear regression analysis, performance, physical evidence, population, promotion, PT Bank Syariah Indonesia, questionnaire, reliability, researcher, respondent, sample, sampling technique, service quality, significance, significant effect, trust, value, work, work environment, work motivation.
- Cluster 2. The green color consists of 44 topics, namely: according, agreement, asset, bank, Indonesian sharia bank kcp, business, contract, conventional bank, customer, data collection, documentation, effort, field research, financing, fund, gold, implementation, Indonesian Islamic bank, Islamic bank, Islamic banking, Islamic law, market share, marketing strategy, murabahah, murabahah contract, observation, obstacle, party, price, principle, process, product, provision, public, qualitative approach, risk, risk management, bank sharia, strategy, system, term, zakat
- Cluster 3. The blue color consists of 16 topics, namely: sharia banks, Indonesian sharia banks, independent sharia banks, BNI Syariah, BRI Syariah, BSI, BUMN Sharia Bank, company, form, merger, minority shareholder, in Indonesian Sharia banks, profitability, secondary data, state, tbk.
- Cluster 4. The yellow color consists of 8 topics, namely: bopo, car, fdr, financial performance, impact, npf, roa, sharia commercial bank.

- Cluster 5. The purple color consists of 7 topics, namely: data analysis, ease, interest, perception, quantitative research, tbk kcp base brandan, technology.
- Cluster 6. The light blue color consists of 4, namely: atm, criteria, location, profit.
- Cluster 7. White consists of 2 topics, namely: banking world, development.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around the Financial Performance of Indonesian Sharia Banks

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 15 topics related to the financial performance of Bank Syariah Indonesia, namely:

First, the influence of Net Operating Margin/NOM, Operational Costs on Operating Income/BOPO, Capital Adequacy Ratio/CAR, financing, Ijarah sukuk issuance, Mudharabah financing, Musyarakah financing, Financing to Deposit Ratio/FDR, and Islamicity Performance Index/IPI on profitability.

Second, asset and debt management.

Third, predict stock prices using the Fuzzy Time Series Lee Model, Support Vector Regression, and Conditional Restricted Boltzman methods.

Fourth, forecasting net profit using the ensemble stacking method.

Fifth, analysis of optimal portfolio formation.

Sixth, application of PSAK 105 in calculating Mudharabah profit sharing.

Seventh, application of liquidity, profitability, solvency and activity ratios in assessing financial performance.

Eighth, the influence of the Covid-19 pandemic on financial performance.

Ninth, the influence of Capital Adequacy Ratio/CAR, Operational Costs on Operating Income/BOPO, asset turnover ratio/Total Asset Turn Over, and Financing to Deposit Ratio/FDR on Non Performing Financing/NPF.

Tenth, the influence of profitability, financial risk and share prices on company value.

Eleventh, the influence of reward levels, inflation, interest rates, production growth on Third Party Funds/DPK.

Twelfth, stock return data uses the Autoregressive Conditional Heteroscedastic-Generalized Autoregressive Conditional Heteroscedastic/ARCH-GARCH model

Thirteenth, the influence of inflation, BI-7 day reverse repo rate, Earning Per Share/EPS on share prices.

Fourteenth, health level using the RGEC method.

Fifteenth, the influence of Non Performing Financing/NPF, Murabahah and Musyarakah funding on profit quality.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding the Performance of Bank Syariah Indonesia Employees

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 32 topics related to the performance of Bank Syariah Indonesia employees, namely:

1. Islamic organizational culture.
2. Work discipline.
3. Islamic work ethics.
4. Good Corporate Governance/GCG.

5. Human Resource Development/HRD.
6. Spiritual climate.
7. Islamic Human Capital Management.
8. Individual characteristics.
9. Leadership (ohio state, islamic).
10. Work ability.
11. Personality.
12. Job satisfaction.
13. Spiritual intelligence.
14. Communication.
15. Compensation.
16. Educational background.
17. Work environment.
18. Human Resources/HR Management.
19. Work motivation.
20. Orientation.
21. Organizational change.
22. Environmental changes.
23. Training.
24. Work experience.
25. Promotion.
26. Religiosity.
27. Employee recruitment.
28. Management control system.
29. Socio-cultural.
30. Work stress.
31. Employee safety and health management strategy.
32. Level of education.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Indonesian Sharia Bank Customer Behavior

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 85 topics related to the behavior of Bank Syariah Indonesia customers, namely:

1. Sharia aspects.
2. Profit sharing on Mudharabah savings products.
3. Marketing mix.
4. Administrative costs.
5. Brand image.
6. Donate when withdrawing cash at an ATM.
7. Corporate image.
8. Customer intimacy.
9. Customer relationship marketing.
10. Customer value.
11. Islamic brand image.
12. Digital banking.
13. E-Banking.
14. Facility.
15. Emotional and rational factors.
16. Fintech.
17. Lifestyle.
18. Halal brand personality.

19. Internet banking.
20. Integrated Marketing Communication/IMC.
21. Islamic marketing mix.
22. Comfort.
23. Security.
24. Convenience.
25. Reference group.
26. Service quality (using Importance Performance Analysis and Fuzzy-Service Quality).
27. Quality of frontliner service.
28. Quality of electronic channel service.
29. Quality of e-service.
30. ATM quality.
31. Product quality.
32. CARTER model service quality.
33. Bank characteristics.
34. Marketing characteristics.
35. Trust.
36. Customer engagement.
37. Intellectual, emotional, spiritual intelligence.
38. Commitment.
39. Employee performance.
40. Canvassing activities.
41. Digital services.
42. Mobile cash car service.
43. Gold liquidity.
44. Sharia financial literacy.
45. Location.
46. Promotion media.
47. Gold pawn valuation method.
48. Halal brand.
49. Mobile banking (efficient, practical, comfortable, easy, safe).
50. Motivation.
51. ATM complaint management.
52. Islamic business ethical values.
53. Subjective norms.
54. Perceptions of community leaders regarding usury.
55. Utilization of technology.
56. Language use and etiquette.
57. Perception of technology.
58. Knowledge.
59. Islamic ethical behavior.
60. UKT payments.
61. Perceptions of religiosity.
62. Understanding.
63. Mathematical modeling for networking.
64. Marketing via Instagram.
65. Marketing products to non-Muslim customers.
66. Spiritual marketing.
67. Promotion.
68. Gold pawn and installment products.
69. Financing products.

70. Mudharabah savings product.
71. Implementation of Qardh and Ijarah contracts.
72. Religiosity.
73. Relationship marketing.
74. Self-service technology/SST.
75. Sharia compliance.
76. Spiritual marketing.
77. Social media influence marketing.
78. Attitude.
79. Credit marketing strategy.
80. Strategic alliances.
81. Service queue system.
82. Financial technology.
83. Level of confidence.
84. Ultimate service.
85. Word of mouth.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Indonesian Sharia Bank Financing/Credit Products

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 21 research topics related to Bank Syariah Indonesia financing products, namely:

First, the influence of financing and business location on changes in MSME income.

Second, partner-use and micro-syariah financing.

Third, marketing strategy for financing products/pension sales force under the auspices of Taspen and Asabri.

Fourth, the influence of the i-kurma application and the TOPSIS method regarding the method of terminating the provision of financing credit.

Fifth, the application of Murabahah contracts in working capital financing, Home Ownership Credit/KPR, People's Business Credit/KUR, car loans and in Regional Financing Operations.

Sixth, the bai' Murabahah financing agreement contract from a civil law and sharia perspective.

Seventh, restructuring of problematic financing in the Musyarakah Mutanaqishah agreement.

Eighth, the influence of character, conditions, guarantees/collateral, and product suitability on the provision of financing credit.

Ninth, implementation of a profit sharing and fee/ujrah system in Murabahah financing.

Tenth, implementing gold installment financing products and implementing Islamic marketing mix, as well as using the theory of planned behavior approach.

Eleventh, execution of mortgage guarantees in credit financing.

Twelfth, implementation of the Mudharabah financing agreement with the principles of freedom of contract, procedures, requirements and prudence.

Thirteenth, financing without collateral (mitraguna) with finite state automata.

Fourteenth, settlement of bad credit with collateral.

Fifteenth, guarantee/financing collateral.

Sixteenth, the implementation of Musyarakah financing is based on the quality of human resources and the effectiveness of compatible incentives.

Seventeenth, determining Murabahah margin and actual cost price.
Eighteenth, the influence of Mudharabah and Musyarakah financing on profit sharing income.
Nineteenth, socialization of MSME capital financing products.
Twentieth, application of Murabahah accounting in mortgage financing.
Twenty-first, the influence of mergers, operational costs on operating income/BOPO, non-performing financing/NPF, company growth, and the BI rate on Murabahah margin income.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Indonesian Sharia Bank Savings Products

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 8 research topics related to Bank Syariah Indonesia savings/savings products, namely:

First, junior mabrur savings products and hajj savings (in achieving maqashid sharia).

Second, the influence of the marketing mix on savings products.

Third, analysis of fatwa no. 115/DSN-MUI/IX/2017 concerning Mudharabah contracts for savings products.

Fourth, implementation of the easy Mudharabah savings profit sharing system.

Fifth, strategy for collecting funds in Mudharabah deposit products and wadiah savings.

Sixth, the influence of Mudharabah savings on investment interest.

Seventh, the role of institutions in increasing deposits.

Eighth, the principle of fairness in wadiah yad dhamanah contracts for savings products.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Mergers in Indonesian Sharia Banks

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 2 research topics related to mergers at Bank Syariah Indonesia, namely:

First, the effect of the merger on Non-Performing Financing/NPF, Non-Performing Margin/NPM, Return On Assets/ROA, Return On Equity/ROE, profitability, thoughts of Islamic economic figures, synchronization of HR work culture, efficiency, stabilization, customer perception, stock prices, customer switching behavior, financial performance using the Islamicity Performance Index/IPI approach, service quality, interest in saving, customer legal status, market share, customer loyalty, legal protection for minority shareholders, consumer financing performance, customer satisfaction, and the condition of the level of public trust.

Second, mergers from the perspective of the rules of al-masyaqqah tajlibu al-taysir, Islamic economic law, SWOT, and monopoly law.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Digitalization and Technology in Indonesian Sharia Banks

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 10 research topics related to digitalization in Indonesian Sharia Banks, namely:

1. First, implementing the database in Mobile Banking.
2. Second, the influence of using the Quick Response-Code Indonesian Standard/QRIS.

3. Third, the influence of information technology in increasing market share on management strategy.
4. Fourth, analysis of customer assessments regarding switching and ease of manual to digital transaction reservations.
5. Fifth, the level of feasibility of ATM locations is based on the Analytical Hierarchy Process/AHP and Decision Tree methods.
6. Sixth, the convenience of mobile applications using the Usability Testing and System Usability Scale methods.
7. Seventh, digitalization of banking products.
8. Eighth, ease of online transactions via the BSI webform.
9. Ninth, digitalization of banking through self-service technology.
10. Tenth, application user sentiment uses the Support Vector Machine/SVM algorithm.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Other Issues in Indonesian Sharia Banks

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 21 research topics related to issues at Bank Syariah Indonesia, namely:

1. First, the application of the Istishna' contract, Murabahah contract, Murabahah bil Wakalah contract, Qardh contract, Rahn/gold pawning contract, zakat payment, multi-contract, and Mudharabah contract.
2. Second, digitalization of sharia finance based on the Sharia Maqashid Framework.
3. Third, the elimination of the Hajj bailout fund.
4. Fourth, implementation of Islamic Work Ethics/IWE and Islamic Corporate Social Responsibility/ICSR.
5. Fifth, selling goods as a pawn from a sharia economic law perspective.
6. Sixth, BSI's role in national economic development, development of the halal industry, and growth of MSMEs during the Covid-19 pandemic.
7. Seventh, the values of Islamic economic law towards products.
8. Eighth, take over uses the Qardh/tabarru' contract.
9. Ninth, risk management in Mudharabah financing contracts, the role of internal audit, and the use of digital payments.
10. Tenth, the influence of top management and technical abilities regarding accounting information systems/SIS on user satisfaction of Accounting Information Systems/SIS.
11. Eleventh, the influence of internal factors, idea development, opportunity, creativity and macroeconomics on market share.
12. Twelfth, collecting and distributing funds.
13. Thirteenth, bank operational risk in market share growth.
14. Fourteenth, SR 017 Retail Sukuk investment product at BSI.
15. Fifteenth, Corporate Social Responsibility/CSR from the perspective of Islamic Social Reporting/ISR Index and Maqashid Syariah Index/MSI.
16. Sixteenth, implementation of green banking.
17. Seventeenth, application of financial accounting standards.
18. Eighteenth, BSI's responsibility for the distribution of social assistance for the family of hope program.
19. Nineteenth, analysis of the tax amnesty on the absorption of reparation funds.
20. Twentieth, comparison of pawning gold at BSI and sharia pawnshops.
21. Twenty-one, Sharia compliance with gold pawning.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded that there are 8 Mapping Research Topics using literature studies regarding Indonesian Sharia Banks, namely: (1) Financial performance; (2) Employee performance; (3) Customer behavior; (4) Financing/credit products; (5) Savings/deposit products; (6) Mergers; (7) Digitalization & technology; and (8) Other issues.

References

- Baranuri, M. Y., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Akad Ijarah pada Industri Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038971>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2022). Pemetaan Penelitian Akad Mudharabah Pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik Vosviewer Dan Literature Review. *J-EBIS (Jurnal Ekonomi Dan Bisnis Islam)*, 7(1), 43–68. <https://doi.org/10.32505/j-ebis.v7i1.3895>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2022). Pemetaan Penelitian Seputar Akad Musyarakah pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *JESI (Jurnal Ekonomi Syariah Indonesia)*, 12(1), 25–36. [https://doi.org/10.21927/jesi.2022.12\(1\).25-36](https://doi.org/10.21927/jesi.2022.12(1).25-36)
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Bibliometric And Literature Review Of Financing Risk In Islamic Banking. *JPS (Jurnal Perbankan Syariah)*, 4(1), 79–97. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.46367/jps.v4i1.1031>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN RISIKO REPUTASI PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LITERATURE REVIEW. *Al-Masraf: Jurnal Lembaga Keuangan Dan Perbankan*, 8(1), 94–113. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.15548/al-masraf.v8i1.425>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Seputar Risiko Kredit pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *BANCO: Jurnal Manajemen Dan Perbankan Syariah*, 5(1), 20–34. <https://doi.org/10.35905/banco.v5i1.4987>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). RESEARCH MAPPING ON CREDIT RISK IN ISLAMIC AND CONVENTIONAL BANKING. *AL-INFAQ: Jurnal Ekonomi Islam*, 14(1), 73–86. <https://doi.org/10.32507/ajei.v14i1.1862>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2022). Research Mapping of Musyarakah Contracts in Islamic Financial Institutions: VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Literature Review. *Maliki Islamic Economics Journal*, 2(2), 76–94. <https://doi.org/10.18860/miec.v2i2.17199>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Akad Ju'alah pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research)*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10040276>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Akad Sharf pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research)*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10042641>

- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Biaya Operasional terhadap Pendapatan Operasional (BOPO) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *JAF (Journal of Accounting and Finance)*, 7(1), 34–48. <https://doi.org/10.25124/jaf.v7i1.5995>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan penelitian rasio Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037417>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Dividend Payout Ratio (DPR) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037141>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Dividend Per Share (DPS) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Al-Mal: Jurnal Akuntansi Dan Keuangan Islam*, 4(1), 109–126. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.24042/al-mal.v4i01.16760>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan penelitian rasio Economic Value Added (EVA) pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037270>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Financial Value Added (FVA) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *BJRM (Bongaya Journal of Research in Management)*, 6(2), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.37888/bjrm.v6i2>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Net Operating Margin (NOM) pada Perbankan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Ecobankers: Journal of Economy and Banking*, 4(2), 84–94. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8323115>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan penelitian rasio Net Profit Margin (NPM) pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037209>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN RASIO NON PERFORMING FINANCING (NPF) PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LITERATURE REVIEW. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038983>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN RASIO RETURN ON INVESTMENT (ROI) PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LITERATURE REVIEW. *Kompetensi (Competence : Journal of Management Studies)*, 17(1), 66–82. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.21107/kompetensi.v17i1.20002>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN RASIO WORKING CAPITAL TURNOVER (WCT) PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LITERATURE

- REVIEW. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037081>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar cash ratio pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037415>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037413>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar current ratio pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037359>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar pengaruh variabel mikroekonomi: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037254>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar quick ratio pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038973>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pengaruh Book Value per Share (BVS) pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Islamic Economics and Business Review*, 2(1). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185250>
- Budianto, E. W. H., Dewi, N. D. T., & Abidin, U. A. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Dana Pihak Ketiga (DPK) Pada Perbankan Syariah Dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik Vosviewer Dan Literature Review. *Syiar Iqtishadi: Journal of Islamic Economics, Finance and Banking*, 7(1), 25–44. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.35448/jiec.v7i1.19887>
- Budianto, E. W. H., Saputra, H. M. G. A., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Koperasi Jasa Keuangan Syariah (KJKS): Studi Bibliometrik VOS viewer dan Literature Review. *EL MUDHORIB: Jurnal Kajian Ekonomi Dan Perbankan Syariah*, 3(2), 131–148. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185180>
- Dewi, N. D. T., Ibad, N. N., Pratopo, G., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Seputar Manajemen Zakat Pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer Dan Literature Review. *Jurnal Ekonomika Dan Bisnis Islam*, 6(1), 1–20. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.26740/jekobi.v6n1.p1-20>
- Febrian, J., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). THE EFFECT OF KNOWLEDGE, TRUST, PRODUCTS, SERVICES AND RELIGIOSITY ON INTEREST IN SAVING. *International Conference of Islamic Economics and Business 9th*, 85–96. <http://repository.uin-malang.ac.id/15487/>
- Gozali, M., Saputra, M. A., Dewi, N. D. T., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN SEPUTAR VARIABEL DETERMINAN RETURN ON EQUITY (ROE) PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK

- VOSVIEWER DAN LITERATURE REVIEW. *IDEI: Jurnal Ekonomi & Bisnis*, 4(1), 34–47. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.38076/ideijeb.v4i1.151>
- Mawardi, M. I., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Tabungan Pensiunan Nasional (BTPN) Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10049566>
- Putri, S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Bukopin Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10049572>
- Qudratullah, M. Q., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Akad Murabahah pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038979>
- Rahmawati, L., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar Bank Tabungan Negara (BTN) syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037422>
- Ratnasari, A. D., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Akad Rahn (Gadai) pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038977>
- Rofiah, A., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Akad Wadiah pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10042647>
- Rofika, H., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN SEPUTAR MAYBANK SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LITERATURE REVIEW. *Jurnal Ekonomi: Journal of Economic*, 14(1), 28–39. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.47007/jeko.v14i01.6463>
- Rohimah, W., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian seputar Bank CIMB Niaga Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Jurnal Ekonomi Manajemen Perbankan*, Vol 5, No 1 (2023): JEMPER Januari-Juni, 30–40. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185264>
- Rohmandika, M. S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian seputar Variabel Determinan Return On Asset pada Perbankan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Eco-Iqtishodi: Jurnal Ilmiah Ekonomi Dan Keuangan Syariah*, 5(1), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.32670/ecoiqtishodi.v5i1.3607>
- Shalsabila, I. H., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar akad kafalah pada industri keuangan syariah: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037426>
- Sufia, I., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Akad Salam pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research)*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10042345>

Zahro, T. S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar akad istishna' pada industri keuangan syariah: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037428>